

Applying Machine Learning to the Telecoms Industry

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

The Telecoms industry in Nigeria alone contributed more than 34\$ billion dollars to nation's GDP. A 1% improvement in efficiency can add 340 million dollars or more to the industry.

2. Aim

The company's aim is to use a set of Machine Learning techniques to gain valuable insights from the data that Telecoms Company generates. This could be used to predict Costumer Churn i.e which costumers are likely not to subscribe. ML could also be used to conduct Campaign Analysis, which in turn can be used improve Marketing and Sales.

3. Material and methods

The raw material for a project like this is the real-time data Telecoms Companies generate. The method will be to use different Machine Learning techniques including deep learning to see patterns and derive insights that might be overlooked.

4. Results

The result of the findings will be then be reported to the CEO or CTO's of the said company

5. Conclusions

Artificial Intelligence has been applied to the Telecoms industry for over a decade now, but the rise of big data and increasing computational power will make it profound in the coming years. Improvement in the telecommunication sector will help bridge the technology inequality gap where less than 1 in 20 people in the developing world lack access to the internet.

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6. Keywords

Artificial Intelligence, Telecoms, Big data

Author biography

Ugonna Alinnor Ugonna Alinnor has a Bsc in Biochemistry from Olabisi Onabanjo University, Nigeria. He is the founder of Cartwheel Technologies, an Artificial Intelligence Company based in Lagos, Nigeria. Upon graduation, he has published more than 5 papers in reputed journals using Machine Learning techniques using datasets from different sectors of the economy.